

Al-Balkhi's Trailblazing Impact on Mental Health Issues

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Abstract

In mental health development, Abu Zayd al-Balkhi is held in high regard as a pioneering figure. This paper explores al-Balkhi's role through his renowned work, "Masālīh al-Abdān wa al-Anfus, " which outlines the early understanding of mental health disorders in the 9th century. Al-Balkhi's exceptional analytical thinking and profound insight into human psychology are explicitly showcased in this work. By critically analyzing "Masālīh al-Abdān wa al-Anfus" this paper presents al-Balkhi's pioneering contribution to the early understanding of mental health. His profound comprehension of human psychology and the use of cognitive therapy established him as a significant figure in mental health history, laying the groundwork for future advancements in psychiatry and mental disorder treatment.

Keywords: al-Balkhi, cognitive therapy, cognitive psychology, mental health, mental disorders, mental illness, psychology.

Al-Balkhi's Trailblazing Impact on Mental Health

In recent years, mental health has gained significant attention as a crucial topic of discussion worldwide. Interestingly, the concern for mental health is not a contemporary phenomenon. Centuries ago, Islamic scholars explored the complex nature of mental health and initiated conversations that remain pertinent today. Al-Balkhi played a pivotal role in shaping the early comprehension of mental health in the Islamic world. He emphasized the crucial importance of mental health and conducted research on diverse psychological conditions. What sets al-Balkhi apart is not only his recognition of these issues but also his proactive proposals for therapeutic interventions. This study investigates al-Balkhi's pioneering discoveries in the realm of psychological well-being. This study scrutinizes his thorough examination of various mental ailments and his innovative approaches to cognitive therapy.

Literature Review

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines mental health as “a state of mental well-being that enables people to cope with the stresses of life, realize their abilities, learn well and work well, and contribute to their community.” (WHO, n.d.). In the meantime, according to the APA (American Psychological Association) Dictionary of Psychology, mental health is “a state of mind characterized by emotional well-being, good behavioral adjustment, relative freedom from anxiety and disabling symptoms, and a capacity to establish constructive relationships and cope with the ordinary demands and stresses of life.” (APA, n.d.)

Concerning mental health issues, the Islamic golden age brought forth numerous Muslim scientists, among whom Abu Zayd al-Balkhi is prominent. He was among the scientists who made significant contributions to the field of psychology, particularly to the area of mental health. During the medieval period, Khan (2023) stated that these conceptualizations and

depictions of mental disorders lacked precision, structure, and focal coherence. Meanwhile, al-Balkhi's role exceeds that period, as he scrutinized numerous mental illnesses alongside their accompanying treatments.

Badri (2013) noted that Abu Zayd al-Balkhi contributed extensively to knowledge across various disciplines. One of his notable achievements was his recognition as one of the earliest cognitive psychologists in the world. Rassool and Luqman (2023) affirm that, "Al-Balkhi is hailed as a pioneer in psychosomatic medicine, counselling psychology, and cognitive therapy," (p. 61). Salami and Khan (2019) said, "Al-Balkhi remain in history to be first scholar that opens the window of cognitive-behaviour psychology," (p.17). With a similar statement, Arroisi et al. (2023) notes, "The most impressive aspect of al-Balkhi's method was the use of pioneering early forms of cognitive therapy."

Yusuf (2022) explains that al-Balkhi was an innovator in recognizing psychological disorders, particularly in differentiating between endogenous and reactive depression. Additionally, he emphasized the importance of spirituality and sustained hope in treating mental health. Salami and Khan (2019) emphasise al-Balkhi's significant impact on cognitive therapy, particularly his innovative preventive approach now recognised as "rational cognitive therapy" (p. 20).

In addition, Taibah et al. (2023) argued that al-Balkhi's theories closely correspond with those of cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) in relation to depression, its symptoms, and treatment methods emphasizing positive and rational thinking to address psychological disorders. Nevertheless, al-Balkhi's viewpoint differs because of the incorporation of religious beliefs. He accentuates the significance of faith in tackling everyday problems and maintains that real fulfilment can be achieved in the afterlife.

Al-Balkhi's work in psychology holds great importance. Awad and Ali (2023) stated that "Sustenance of the Body and Soul" is self-help guide, grounded in Islamic beliefs, aims to enhance psychological wellbeing through a comprehensive method that involves the body, mind, and spirit. Mobayed (2017) noted that al-Balkhi's language is accessible and easy to understand for all readers. According to Awad dan Ali, al-Balkhi presents a "do it self" approach to cognitive and spiritual therapies through his treatise " Masālīh al-Anfus " (Rassool and Luqman, 2023, p. 62). As noted in his manuscript, no scholar had attempted to write a medical treatise of this kind before. (Badri, 2013. p. 3)

Badri (2013) claims that his book is unique in its integration of nourishment for both the body and soul within a single volume, making an unprecedented contribution to this field. Badri highlighted the significance of his approach, especially for patients, because of the profound interdependence between the body and mind (p. 13). In addition, Al-Balkhi proposed a correlation between physical and mental health, suggesting that each can affect the other. Physical pain may lead to mental distress, or vice versa, and is currently known as a psychosomatic disorder.

According to Abdullah (2011), al-Balkhi recognized centuries ago that severe emotional reactions could lead to physical illnesses, and that emotional disorders could be a catalyst for various physical disorders. The term that al-Balkhi named "ishtibak" (Badri et al. 2000). Deuraseh and Abu Thalib (2005) cite al-Balkhi, "if the body gets sick, the Nafs (psyche) loses much of its cognitive and comprehensive ability and fails to enjoy the desirous aspects of life" and that "if the Nafs gets sick, the body may also find no joy in life and may eventually develop a physical illness" (Rassool and Luqman, 2023, p. 62)

Khan (2023) reviewed al-Balkhi's pioneering contributions to the understanding and treatment of mental illness. Badri (2013) noted that al-Balkhi was able to distinguish between psychoses and neuroses; categorize depression into normal, reactive, and endogenous types; and offer a thorough explanation of cognitive therapy's implementation for treating psychological disorders. (p. 3)

Moreover, al-Balkhi's depiction of mental illnesses is reasonably precise and conforms to contemporary practice. Awaad and Ali's (2016) account of mental illness is reasonably accurate and is in line with contemporary practice. Awaad and Ali (2016) concluded that al-Balkhi's classification, diagnosis and treatment of 'al-Faza' is very similar to the current understanding of phobias as outlined in the DSM-5.

When examining al-Balkhi's contributions to the area of cognitive psychology, it becomes clear that the concepts proposed by this exceptional Muslim scholar have endured the test of time and retained significance in contemporary times. When discussing the origins of OCD, al-Balkhi references not only physiological causes but also metaphysical causes, specifically by alluding to the terms jinn qarin and satan. Al-Balkhi said, "The origin of this obsessive disorder is either the dominance of certain body humors, (as detailed earlier), or from the devil appointed to a person (the qarin) that strives to spoil one's life in this world and the Hereafter." (Badri, 2013. p. 63).

Al-Balkhi's view aligns with contemporary research indicating that jinn may affect an individual's physical and mental well-being. Dein and Illaiee (2018) explained that in numerous non-Western cultural contexts, prominent dissociative disorders revolve around states of trance or possession. Despite the DSM-IV recognizing the presence of these conditions, specifically referred to as dissociative trance disorder, additional research is needed to evaluate their clinical relevance in the context of the DSM-5.

Discussion

Al-Balkhi's work is widely considered a significant starting point in the investigation of mental disorders within psychological academic literature. Although his famous book *Masālih al-Abdān wa al-Anfus* examines only a limited number of mental disorders recognized during his era, his contributions were invaluable. Al-Balkhi facilitated an early understanding of mental disorders, albeit not encompassing the complete range of disorders identified in detail in the current DSM V manual.

Al-Balkhi's research is limited by its specific historical and intellectual context, which provides limitations to its applicability. However, his work has established a fundamental framework for subsequent investigations of mental health disorders, although it is not exhaustive. Thus, although his book may not be as comprehensive as modern guides, it remains an indispensable contribution to our understanding of psychological disorders.

In addition, al-Balkhi delves into the mental condition of obsessive inner speech, also known as self-talk or inner voice, which is regarded as a symptom that significantly affects individuals. Obsessive thoughts are challenging to manage and can persist despite treatment, demonstrating the persistence of this symptomatology among those afflicted (Badri, 2013, pp. 54-57).

According to modern psychology, self-talk can be divided into two categories: positive self-talk and negative self-talk. Positive self-talk serves to empower individuals, whereas negative self-talk can have a detrimental effect on self-esteem. Unconstructive self-dialogue is not grounded in reality and can immobilize individuals, inducing a sense of insufficiency and inability to progress. (Psychology Today, n.d.)

Conclusion and Future Study

The paper concludes that al-Balkhi merits recognition as a trailblazer in cognitive psychology due to his profound intellectual aptitude and fascination with the complexity of the human mind, as demonstrated through his works that go beyond his era. Hence, gaining a comprehensive understanding of Al-Balkhi's model can offer beneficial perspectives for addressing mental health concerns in this current age. Further examination of al-Balkhi's concepts and other related cognitive therapies is crucial for determining their current applicability today's society. Only with systematic examination and analysis can we ascertain the enduring significance of al-Balkhi's concepts and their probable impact on the advancing arena of mental health treatment in the current setting.

References

- Abdullah, F. (2011). Therapeutic Ethics: Managing Anger, Negative Thoughts and Depression According to al-Balkhī. *Afkar: Jurnal Akidah & Pemikiran Islam*, 12(1), 77-100.
- Arroisi, J. and Himaya, N.N. (2023) ‘Abu Zayd al-Balkhi’s perspective on depression: Countering sadness with cognitive theory in the book of Mashalih Al Abdan wa al Anfus’, *Tazkiya Journal of Psychology*, 11(1), pp. 1–12.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.15408/tazkiya.v11i1.29913>
- American Psychological Association. (n.d.). *Apa Dictionary of Psychology*. American Psychological Association. <https://dictionary.apa.org/mental-health>
- Awaad, R., & Ali, S. (2023). The original self-help book: Al-balkhi’s 9th century “Sustenance of the body and soul”. *Spirituality in Clinical Practice*, 10(1), 89–98.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/scp0000310>
- Awaad, R., & Ali, S. (2016). A modern conceptualization of phobia in al-Balkhi’s 9th century treatise: Sustenance of the Body and Soul. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 37, 89-93.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.janxdis.2015.11.003>
- Badri, M. (2013). *Abu Zayd al-Balkhi’s sustenance of the Soul: The cognitive behavior therapy of a ninth century physician*. The International Institute of Islamic Thought (IIIT).
- Badri, M., Henzell-Thomas, J., & Lu’lu’a, A.-W. (2000). Contemplation: The Works of Early Muslim Scholars. In *Contemplation: An Islamic Psychospiritual Study* (New, pp. 21–35). International Institute of Islamic Thought. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvk8w1xc.7>
- Dein, S., & Illaiee, A. S. (2018, January 2). *Jinn and mental health: Looking at jinn possession in modern psychiatric practice: The psychiatrist*. Cambridge Core.
<https://doi.org/10.1192/pb.bp.113.042721>
- Khan, B. (2023, August). Al-Balkhi: a pioneer of psychotherapy and psychosomatic medicine. *Insights Magazine, Summer Edition* (13), 4–5.
- Mobayed, T. (2017, January 8). *Abu Zayd Al Balkhi: The 9th century psychologist centuries ahead of his time*. IlmFeed. <https://ilmfeed.com/abu-zayd-al-balkhi-the-9th-century-psychologist-centuries-ahead-of-his-time/>
- Rassool, G. H., & Luqman, M. M. (2023). *Foundations of Islāmic Psychology: From Classical Scholars to contemporary thinkers*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Salami, M., & Khan, R. (2019). Islam and Cognitive Behaviour Psychology: An Introduction. In *10th International Symposium on Islam, Civilization and Science (ISICAS 2019)* (p. 17–24).

Sussex Publishers. (n.d.). *Self-talk*. Psychology Today.

<https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/basics/self-talk>

Taibah, S., Hawadi, L., & al-Asyhar, T. (2023). Psychotherapy: a comparison of Abu Zayd Al-Balkhi and CBTt. *Psikis: Jurnal Psikologi Islami*, 9(2).

<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.19109/psikis.v9i2.17915>

World Health Organization. (n.d.). *Mental health*. World Health Organization.

<https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/mental-health-strengthening-our-response>

Yusuf. (2022, September 17). *Abu Zayd Balkhi on depression – Shaykh Dr Asim Yusuf*.

SeekersGuidance. <https://seekersguidance.org/articles/prophet-muhammad/abu-zayd-balkhi-depression/>